

Trigonometric functions and real numbers

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$$\begin{aligned} \tan\theta &= k; \\ \theta &= \arctan(k). \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

As shown in (1), substituting the angle derived from the inverse tangent of a real number k yields a real value; the corresponding graph of these angles is provided below.

Figure 1. graph of equation (1)

$$\frac{1}{\cos\theta} = k;$$

$$\cos\theta = \frac{1}{k};$$

$$\theta = \arccos\left(\frac{1}{k}\right). \quad (2)$$

Figure 2. graph of equation (2)

$$\frac{1}{\sin\theta} = k;$$

$$\sin\theta = \frac{1}{k};$$

$$\theta = \arcsin\left(\frac{1}{k}\right). \quad (3)$$

Figure 3. graph of equation (3)

On the other hand, since sine and cosine functions oscillate between -1 and 1, I took the reciprocal of these values to derive equations (2) and (3) for the angles

where these functions yield real numbers k , and subsequently plotted their graphs. Note that in Equations (2) and (3), if the value of k is less than unity, the magnitudes of the sin and cos functions will exceed 1.

Since these functions cannot exceed unity in the real domain, the computational domain is extended to the complex number system in this case.